

Table 5: Top-ranked statements per theme (P < .05; Asterisk (*) Indicates Significance at P < .01)

	Theme 1: Intrinsic Motivation			Theme 2: Altruistic Leanings			Theme 3: Sales v. Fiduciary		
Rank	Distinguishing statements for Factor 1	Z-Score Value	Rank	Distinguishing statements for Factor 2	Z-Score Value	Rank	Distinguishing Statements for Factor 3	Z-Score Value	
1	31. As a fiduciary, I have too many clients to serve them all well.	1.73	1	5. My main motivation for working is to help as many investors succeed as possible.	2.14*	1	36. I feel my role is sales-oriented because I have to sell myself to FCs and sell myself to clients.	1.93*	
2	19. As long as I were well paid, if I didn't have performance targets, I would be motivated anyway because I find the work I do is important and personally gratifying.	1.59*	2	31. As a fiduciary, I have too many clients to serve them all well.	1.21	2	17. Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box' mentality where the quality of the work can be secondary to getting it done.	1.86	
3	34. It is awkward when a client asks, "How often do you review my investments?" because the real answer may not seem like it would be often enough to them.	1.43*	3	21. If we were really 'looking through client's eyes', it would be best to tie bonuses to how well clients are doing toward achieving their financial goals.	1.01	3	30. My performance targets do a good job of measuring how well I serve clients.	- 0.03*	
4	17. Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box' mentality where the quality of the work can be secondary to getting it done.	1.13	4	17. Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box' mentality where the quality of the work can be secondary to getting it done.	0.57	4	31. As a fiduciary, I have too many clients to serve them all well.	- 0.13*	
5	21. If we were really 'looking through client's eyes', it would be best to tie bonuses to how well clients are doing toward achieving their financial goals.	0.46	5	11. The thing my clients say matters most to them is the performance of their investments.	0.55	5	14. Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive.	- 0.20*	
6	28. There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cover the same branch locations.	0.35	6	23. It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company performed.	0.47*	6	29. Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to compromise my ethical standards at least a little.	- 0.27*	
7	35. My success depends on getting new referrals from FCs so I should be careful not to contradict or alienate them.	0.17*	7	6. My main motivation for working is for me to succeed.	0.36	7	22. It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and single-topic solutions clients receive.	- 0.30*	